

URBAN PLANNING AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC REQUIREMENTS

Allambergenov Azamat Tilewbergenovich
Karakalpak State University named after Berdak
Turgaev Jambil
Scientific supervisor

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12598327>

Abstract. This article describes urban planning and socio-economic requirements, the process of reconstruction of residential buildings.

Key words: Housing, building, urban development, reconstruction, urban construction.

ГОРОДСКОЕ ПЛАНИРОВАНИЕ И СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЕ ТРЕБОВАНИЯ

Аннотация. В статье описаны градостроительные и социально-экономические требования, процесс реконструкции жилых домов.

Ключевые слова: Жилье, строительство, градостроительство, реконструкция, городское строительство.

In the process of reconstruction of residential buildings, the tasks of social and urban planning, as well as the economic and technical efficiency of its implementation are taken into account in every way. The social tasks of the reconstruction are the construction of the housing fund and the radical renewal of the planning structure.

These tasks ensure the improvement and gradual equalization of the living conditions of the population, which must meet the modern and future requirements in the old and new urban areas. The urban planning tasks of the reconstruction include improving the urban planning structure, improving the urban environment, improving the architectural and spatial qualities of buildings, improving the network of streets, squares, transport and pedestrian, communication and highways, as well as engineering equipment and utilities. regulation of systems. At the moment, reconstruction of the housing stock of the country's cities is being carried out widely. According to the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5386 dated March 29, 2018, complete reconstruction works are being carried out in many residential areas of our republic.

It is known from the rich and ancient history of our country that the beautification of neighborhoods and the implementation of creative works by our ancestors is one of the most valuable values and traditions. By carrying out large-scale creative works in all regions while consistently continuing these values, it is of particular importance to create decent conditions for rural residents and further improve their living culture, and most importantly, to encourage young people to do good deeds. If everyone contributes to the beautification of the house, neighborhood and village where he lives, our country will be prosperous, and people living in a prosperous country will be in a good mood. At the same time, despite the concentration of significant demographic, labor and economic potential in rural areas, where 49% of the population of our country live, the necessary conditions have not been created for them, and insufficient attention has been paid to improving the standard and quality of life. In particular, in recent years, the vital and household needs of peasant farmers and other categories of population, who have a high

contribution to the production of cotton, grain and other agricultural products, have not been fully provided.

Such a situation is an obstacle to the transformation of our country into a modern developed country without the radical renewal of rural settlements and its socio-economic development. In particular, during the visits to the regions, getting acquainted with the real situation in the places, directly entering the neighborhoods and houses, and the results of communication with the residents show the existence of the following systemic problems. In order to solve these existing problems, in 2019, large-scale construction and beautification works were carried out in 479 villages and farms, and 116 neighborhoods in cities within the framework of the "Prosperous Village" and "Prosperous Mahalla" programs. 6.1 trillion soums were spent on this, or 1.5 trillion soums more than in 2018. In rural areas - 17 thousand 100, in cities - 17 thousand 600, a total of 34 thousand 700 or about 3 times as many cheap and comfortable houses were built compared to 2016. Within the framework of the Decree of the President of March 29, 2018 on the "Prosperous Village" program, 2 villages (neighborhoods) in 2018 and 3 in the coming years in each district and city of our country, especially in remote areas with severe natural climatic conditions. It was determined that measures will be taken to radically improve the living conditions of the population, to ensure significant positive changes in the lifestyle and level, to modernize the image of these areas and to create jobs for its residents. The population will be reliably supplied with drinking water at the expense of funds allocated from the republic budget and state special funds.

Roads connecting the villages with the district center will be built, reconstructed and repaired. On the basis of the lease, bus service will be started between the village and the district center. Rural roads and footpaths will be built and repaired at the expense of local budgets. The roads will be beautified and planted with greenery. Sanitary facilities and irrigation systems will be built, bus stations will be built. In general, the issues of electricity supply, communication system, continuous supply of liquefied gas and coal fuel to the population will be resolved. Kindergarten, school and family polyclinics will be built. Market infrastructure facilities, service stations, bathrooms will be built. The village of Manas, located in the Jizzakh region, has gone down in history as a foundation, so to speak, a model for the implementation of the "Prosperous Village" program in our country.

In this village, where more than 6,500 people lived, in the following years, people were suffering as a result of infrastructure facilities, streets and roads, drinking water, heat, electricity supply, cultural and household services not meeting the demand. On the basis of the "Prosperous Village" program, large-scale works were carried out in a short period of time to eliminate existing problems in the region.

As part of the program, 41 kilometers of collector-drainage networks were cleaned to eliminate the rise in the level of stormwater. New auxiliary buildings and bakeries were built in place of the unplanned constructions around the houses. Fruit and decorative tree saplings were planted. A water pipeline was laid in order to supply the population with drinking water. Water distribution facilities were put out of repair. 2 secondary schools were repaired and re-equipped. Educational workshops were established in these schools and provided with carpentry, plumbing, and sewing machines.

Within the framework of the "Prosperous village" and "Prosperous neighborhood" programs, work is being continued consistently in 2020 and 2021. Within the framework of the "Prosperous village" and "Prosperous neighborhood" programs of 2021, the development of social infrastructure and the provision of housing to the population, specific tasks to be performed in 7,794 villages and neighborhoods have been determined, and 18 trillion soums will be allocated for this. is being directed. An additional 300 million dollars was allocated for providing the population with clean drinking water, construction and repair of internal roads.

As a result, 1,400 kilometers of networks were built and reconstructed in the field of drinking water supply alone, and 8,500 kilometers of internal roads were repaired. In the past period, 2,000 kilometers of power lines were laid and 1,000 transformers were renewed. Residential buildings that have served for 50 to 100 years or more, which make up a significant part of the housing stock in the country's major cities, are usually and are the largest objects of reconstruction. Most of them are capital high-rise buildings, which are technically suitable for long-term operation. Their aesthetic and architectural qualities are extremely important from the point of view of urban planning. The individual appearance of old residential buildings plays a large and sometimes key role in shaping the identity of old urban areas, especially the central parts of cities. At the same time, most of the old residential buildings are in a bad physical and spiritual condition. Their reconstruction is an important architectural, urban planning and technical problem.

The practice of reconstruction of public buildings is currently not very wide, and most importantly, not very uniform. The latter situation is due to two reasons: firstly, a large nomenclature of very different public buildings of different profiles and different scales, and secondly, different functional purposes of the buildings. Reconstructed public buildings include buildings specially constructed and adapted for this purpose. The main volume of work on the reconstruction of public buildings corresponds to the old districts of the city. Most of the buildings located here were built a long time ago and have deteriorated physically and spiritually. The gap between the functions of social sector buildings and the buildings they are forced to accommodate is constantly growing. This has become especially acute at times when high-level technical equipment is required for all types of activities. For the same reason, old buildings used for their original purpose do not meet modern requirements: hospitals, educational institutions, etc. Not only have the requirements for their location and improvement of the engineering level changed, the maximum and minimum sizes of these institutions, the principles of their placement, etc. are now evaluated in a completely different way.

REFERENCES

1. Michael R. Lindeburg, Kurt M. McMullin. Seismic Design of Building Structures, 1 1th Ed Eleventh Edition, New Edition Edition. USA. 2014
2. Binolar rekonstruksiyasi: darslik/ B.X. Raximov, S.T. Qosimova, Sh.Shodjalilov, O.A. Bader. T., "Iqtisod-Moliya", 2008 - 216 b.
3. Miralimov M.M. Bino va inshootlarni qayta qurish va ta'mirlash. O'quv qo'llanma. TAQL, 2019 y. 146 bet.

4. N.N.Norov Passiv quyosh isitish tizimli kam qavatli turar-joy binolarining konstruktiv yechimi. Monografiya, Toshkent, 2020y, 132 b.
5. Mirziyoev Sh.M. Qonun ustuvorligi va inson manfaatlarini ta'minlash – yurt taraqqiyoti va xalq farovonligining garovi. T.: “O‘zbekiston” 2016 yil 47 b.
6. Mirziyoev Sh.M. Buyuk kelajagimizni mard va olijanob xalqimiz bilan birga quramiz. T.: “O‘zbekiston” 2016 yil 486 b.
7. R.Yu.Marakaev, S.Sayfiddinov, U.T.Yusupov, T.Xasanov “Quruq issiq iqlim sharoitida shaharsozlik” o‘quv qo‘llanma, Toshkent; TAQI, 2015 yil, 148 b.
8. Miralimov M.M., Sayfiddinov S., Babajanov M.D. Arxitektura. Darslik. Toshkent, 2016 y. –316 bet. 9